

Nea Moni, Chios

By Marina Toumpouri, Centre for Medieval Arts and Rituals, University of Cyprus

Entry tags: Christian, Greece, Religious Group, Byzantine, Christian Orthodox, North Aegean, Aegean, Religious Place

Nea Moni (meaning “new monastery” in Greek) on the Greek island of Chios, dedicated to the Mother of God, was founded according to tradition by three local hermits Niketas, John, and Joseph. The three monks had built a small church on the spot where they had found a miraculous icon of the Virgin Mary hanging on a tree, during the period of the reign of emperor Michael IV (1034-1041). During this period Constantine Monomachos was exiled on the island of Lesbos. The three monks who had a divine revelation travelled from Chios to Lesbos in order to announce him that he would soon become emperor. Constantine promised them that in that case, he would build a Monastery on the spot where the icon was found. In 1042 Constantine Monomachos was proclaimed emperor and as promised he built the main church of the Monastery, bringing skilled artisans and an architect from the capital of the empire, Constantinople. He furthermore conferred abundant privileges and lands secured by imperial documents. The main church of the Monastery is a small square below a tall segmented dome on an octagonal drum. It also possesses an outer and an inner narthex, as well as a low bema, all of them forming distinct parts of the main structure. In the 16th century, probably around 1512, a new bell tower replaced the original one. In the 19th century in the katholikon were opened windows in order to bring more light to the space. The church suffered great destruction during the Massacre of Chios’ population of 1822 and the earthquake of 1881, which has led to the reconstruction of the dome, large parts of the superstructure and the east, north and south arches. Between 1045 and 1055 the church was decorated with mosaics of high quality. In the esonarthex are depicted scenes from the Life of Christ (Raising of Lazarus, Entry into Jerusalem, Foot-washing, Betrayal), Virgin Mary and Martyrs (Evgenios, Afxentios, Efstratios, Sergios, Theodoros Stratilatis, Bacchos, Orestis and Mardarios) in the blind dome of the esonarthex. In the main part of the church are depicted: Cherubims and Seraphims, and two of the four Evangelists (John and Mark) in the pendentives of the dome; the orant Virgin (semi-dome of the apse), Archangels Michael (prothesis) and Gabriel (diakonikon) in the bema; Great Feasts (Baptism, Transfiguration, Crucifixion, Deposition, Descent into Hades/Anastasis) in the conchs of the dome. It is believed that king Salomon depicted in the scene of the Anastasis is a portrait of emperor Constantine Monomachos. The mosaic decoration of Nea Moni is one of the three ensembles of the middle byzantine period, still preserved in Greece, together with Hosios Loukas in Boeotia and the Monastery of Daphni in Attica. The mosaics of the katholikon of Nea Moni were partly destroyed by the earthquake of 1881. The south and the north apses, as well as the domes of the exonarthex were later decorated with two different layers of frescoes that were uncovered, during the restoration of the monument. The earlier of them, the Palaeologan layer, dates to the 13th century. The second dates to the 17th century. The floors of all the parts of the church were paved with opus sectile. The defensive tower, which was likely used as a library space, the cistern and the refectory date all to the 11th century. Outside the walls of the Monastery are still preserved the funerary chapel dedicated to Saint Loukas –considered also an 11th-century monument–, parts of the aqueduct, as well as various other buildings such as cells, workshops, warehouses etc. Nea Moni was inscribed on the List of UNESCO World Heritage Sites in 1990.

Date Range: 1042 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nea Moni, Chios island

Region tags: Greece, Aegean, Chios

Nea Moni is located on the western slope of Provateio mountain, in the centre of the island of Chios.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Mountain

Notes: The Monastery is located on the western slope of Provateio mountain, in the centre of the island of Chios.

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Purposefully placed plants

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: Most of the structures were built in the 11th century. However, chapels and other auxiliary structures such as the bell tower etc. were later additions to the initial structure.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: Most of the features were built/added in the 11th century. However, many of them were later additions to the initial structure.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

Notes: The Monastery is per se a group of structures and features.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: The Chios massacre was a catastrophe that resulted in the death, enslavement, and flight of about four-fifths of the total population of Greeks on the island of Chios by Ottoman troops, during the Greek War of Independence, in 1822. The Monastery was also damaged.

– Other [specify]: The earthquake of 1881 destroyed the dome, large parts of the superstructure and the east, north and south arches of the main church of the Monastery.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– As the result of war

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

Notes: The earthquake of 1881 destroyed the dome, large parts of the

superstructure and the east, north and south arches.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Worship of God

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Misailidou, A. Η Νέα Μονή Της Χίου. Chios: Third Ephorate of Byzantine Antiquities, 2012
- Source 2: Bouras, C. Η Νέα Μονή Της Χίου, Ιστορία Και Αρχιτεκτονική. Athens, 1981
- Source 3: Mouriki, N. Τα Ψηφιδωτά Της Νέας Μονής Χίου. Athens, 1985

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

- Trackway or road-surface
- Water feature
- Plantings

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/537/>
- Source 1 Description: Monasteries of Daphni, Hosios Loukas and Nea Moni of Chios, Unesco World Heritage Sites
- Source 1 URL: <https://efachi.gr/wp-content/uploads/2012/05/neamoni.pdf>
- Source 1 Description: Misailidou, A. Η Νέα Μονή Της Χίου. Chios: Third Ephorate of Byzantine Antiquities, 2012
- Source 1 URL: <https://youtu.be/GS2yGJjEg3I>
- Source 1 Description: Nea Moni, Chios (video)
- Source 1 URL: <https://discoverchios.gr/el/item/206/e-nea-mone-diathesime-se-binteo-psephiakes-pragmatikotetas-360deg>
- Source 1 Description: Video-Virtual tour of Nea Moni created by the Third Ephorate of Byzantine Antiquities

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:
– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:
– Year range: 2003

↳ Name of excavation
– Official or descriptive name: Excavation of the eastern cells (sub-project "Enhancement of the eastern cells of Nea Moni of Chios"), part of the project "Consolidation, restoration and enhancement of Nea Moni of Chios", funded by the Third European Community Support Framework (2000-2006)

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– No

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Notes: The Monastery was built at the expenses of the emperor Constantine Monomachos. However, prior to the construction of the current katholikon, there was an earlier church built on the same spot by the three founders of the Monastery.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– Yes

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Other [specify]: Christian Orthodox hermits

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: The Monastery was built on the spot where the miraculous icon of the Mother of God was found.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: The Monastery was built on the spot where the miraculous icon of the Mother of God was found.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: The Monastery was built by the Byzantine emperor Constantine Monomachus.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: The Monastery was built after the promise made to the three founders of the Monastery, following the prophecy they gave to Constantine Monomachus that he would become emperor.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

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– Source 1 URL: <https://efachi.gr/wp-content/uploads/2012/05/neamoni.pdf>

– Source 1 Description: Misailidou, A. Η Νέα Μονή Της Χίου. Chios: Third Ephorate of Byzantine Antiquities, 2012

– Source 1 URL: <https://youtu.be/GS2yGJjEg3I>

– Source 1 Description: Nea Moni, Chios (video)

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Name of excavation

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Topographical Context

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– Elevation

Type of elevation

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Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

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- ↳ Type of feature
 - Trackway or road-surface
 - Water feature
 - Plantings

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

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 - No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

- ↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:
 - Yes

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

- ↳ A single structure
 - No
- ↳ One single feature
 - Purposefully placed plants
- ↳ A group of structures:

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↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

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Notes: Most of the structures were built in the 11th century. However, chapels and other auxiliary structures such as the bell tower etc. were later additions to the initial structure.

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↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Worship of God

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Notes: The Monastery was built at the expenses of the emperor Constantine Monomachos. However, prior to the construction of the current katholikon, there was an earlier church built on the same spot by the three founders of the Monastery.

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Was the place created as the result of an event:

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↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: The Monastery was built on the spot where the miraculous icon of the Mother of God was found.

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– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: The Monastery was built by the Byzantine emperor Constantine Monomachus.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: The Monastery was built after the promise made to the three founders of the Monastery, following the prophecy they gave to Constantine Monomachus that he would become emperor.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: The outside of the main church has brick decoration.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: Mosaics and frescoes.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: The decoration is movable and immovable.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

Notes: In the katholikon is depicted Christ, the Son of God.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Archangels, Seraphims and Cherubims.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Virgin Mary, the Evangelists and Saints.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The animals depicted are included in the scenes from the Life of Christ, such as the donkey that carries Christ in the scene of the Entry into Jerusalem.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Notes: Icons are always present in Christian Orthodox churches.

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

Notes: The icons are depicting Christ, Virgin Mary and Saints.

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: The narratives depicted are inspired from the Life of Christ and his mother.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Saints and scenes are also depicted on other movable objects, mainly liturgical that are kept at the Monastery.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: The narratives depicted are inspired from the Life of Christ and his mother.

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Part of the mosaic decoration of the main church of the Monastery was destroyed, so we can only assume what the lost scenes/portraits were.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: The inscriptions that accompany narrative scenes and portraits in the Christian Orthodox monuments are always describing the event and/or the person depicted.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: It is believed that king Salomon depicted in the scene of the Descent into Hades is a portrait of emperor Constantine Monomachos, the person who donated the funds for the foundation of the Monastery.

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: Opus sectile floors.

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Notes: The monastic complex of Nea Moni includes the main church, the bell tower, chapels, the cells of the monks, the refectory currently turned into a museum, the cistern, the surrounding walls, workshops,

the aqueduct, warehouses etc.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:
– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:
– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:
– Yes

Notes: The central structure of the Monastery is the katholikon, the main church.

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
– Yes

Notes: Byzantine

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
– Yes

Notes: Cherubims, Seraphims, Archangels.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife
– Yes

Notes: There is a Last Judgement depiction in the exonarthex dated to the 17th century.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: Dove symbol of the Holy Spirit; Cross.

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Christ, Mother of Christ, Saints, Apostles, Evangelists.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the Life of Christ and Virgin Mary

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Marble, gold

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Glass tesserae used for the creation of the mosaics, binders and pigment mixtures for the frescoes.

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Notes: The monastic complex of Nea Moni includes the main church, the bell tower, chapels, the cells of the monks, the refectory currently turned into a museum, the cistern, the surrounding walls, workshops, the aqueduct, warehouses etc.

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Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

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Notes: The outside of the main church has brick decoration.

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Notes: Mosaics and frescoes.

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– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: The inscriptions that accompany narrative scenes and portraits in the Christian Orthodox monuments are always describing the event and/or the person depicted.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: It is believed that king Salomon depicted in the scene of the Descent into Hades is a portrait of emperor Constantine Monomachos, the person who donated the funds for the foundation of the Monastery.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Opus sectile floors.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

Notes: Byzantine

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Cherubims, Seraphims, Archangels.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Notes: There is a Last Judgement depiction in the exonarthex dated to the 17th century.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: Dove symbol of the Holy Spirit; Cross.

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Christ, Mother of Christ, Saints, Apostles, Evangelists.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: Scenes from the Life of Christ and Virgin Mary

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: This is the most important pilgrimage of the island of Chios. However, the monument is also visited by those interested in its unique architecture and mosaics, who can associate their visit to pilgrimage.

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

- ↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
 - No

Is divination present:

- No

Is this place a tomb/burial:

- No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

- Yes

- ↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
 - No

- ↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
 - Yes

Notes: The Monastery follows the liturgical cycle of the Orthodox Church.

- ↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
 - specify: It is impossible to know.

- ↳ How often do these rituals take place:
 - specify: At least once a week (Sunday) and on selected feast days.

- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The rite and liturgical practices are those prescribed by the Orthodox Church.

- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The rite and liturgical practices are those prescribed by the Orthodox Church.

- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: Yet, this is a place of worship of God and a place for praying to God, the Mother of God and Saints, considered a form of communication between humans and them.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: However, people visit the Monastery to pray.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

–specify: The Monastery celebrates on the 23rd of August every year.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

–All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

–number: The Monastery is open to all wishing to visit it.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Offerings to the Monastery can vary from very precious objects, monetary offerings, food etc.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Offerings to the Monastery can vary from very precious objects, monetary offerings, food etc.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Offerings to the Monastery can vary from very precious objects, monetary offerings, food etc. They depend on the financial capacity of the pilgrims, visitors and the aim of their visit.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The Monastery has gone in the past important restorations. This is to likely happen in the future for preserving it for the next generations.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: The monks and the archaeologists, as well as other experts are maintaining the Monastery.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: This is an important monument and so restoration, excavations and constant monitoring of the Monastery is undertaken.

Are formal burials present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

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Are formal burials present:

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Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

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Notes: Yet, this is a place of worship of God and a place for praying to God, the Mother of God and Saints, considered a form of communication between humans and them.

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Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

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Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

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Notes: However, people visit the Monastery to pray.

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

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Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

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Pilgrimage and Festivals

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- ↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:
– number: The Monastery is open to all wishing to visit it.

- ↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):
– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

- No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

- No

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– I don't know

Notes: It is possible that at the Monastery are preserved such documents. Certainly those concerning the more recent period of the Monastery.

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Nea Moni is inhabited by a male monastic community.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

Notes: Although the monks living at the Monastery are not dedicated to the place for life, the most common is to remain there until the end of their life.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: The monastic community is led by the abbot (higoumenos).

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– I don't know

Notes: The Monastery is the major attraction of the island of Chios and so many locals are working there. In the past the Monastery was the centre of the island's life.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Each monk has a cell to sleep and study.

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

Does this place lease out land:

– I don't know

Notes: This is probable, since the Monastery was conferred huge lands.

Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The Third Ephorate of Byzantine Antiquities of the Greek Ministry of Culture, as well as the Bishopric of Chios, Psara and Oinousses are in charge of the maintenance of the Monastery.

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Nea Moni is inhabited by a male monastic community.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

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↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

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↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

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Notes: The Third Ephorate of Byzantine Antiquities of the Greek Ministry of Culture, as well as the Bishopric of Chios, Psara and Oinousses are in charge of the maintenance of the Monastery.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– I don't know

Notes: This is probable, since the Monastery was conferred huge lands.

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– I don't know

Notes: The Monastery is the major attraction of the island of Chios and so many locals are working there. In the past the Monastery was the centre of the island's life.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– I don't know

Notes: It is possible that at the Monastery are preserved such documents. Certainly those concerning the more recent period of the Monastery.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

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